

Heterocyclic Compounds. Part—IX† Syntheses of N-Nitrosoureas and N-Nitrosothioureas as Possible Antitumor Agents

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The synthesis of several novel N-nitrosoureas and N-nitrosothioureas from various heterocyclic and alicyclic amines have been described. Nitrosoureas were prepared by nitrosation of ureas using NaNO₂ in formic acid whereas nitrosothioureas were obtained by nitrosation of thioureas under slightly acidic condition. The higher acidic reaction condition of thioureas favoured nitrosation at more reactive sulphur leading to urea derivatives via thionitrosyl intermediate. The antitumor activity of some compounds has been evaluated against leukemia L1210.

1-(β-Chloroethyl)-3-alkyl-1-nitrosoureas^{1,2} (CENU's) and several related compounds^{3,4} are clinically useful in the treatment of range of malignant diseases. The present study is directed towards the synthesis of several heterocyclic nitrosoureas and their sulphur analogues with a view to evaluating their antitumor activity. The sulphur analogues of the urea derivatives have been chosen because of the fact that the isothiocyanates themselves exhibit antitumor properties. 3-(4-Arylthiazolyl-2)-1-(2-chloroethyl)-1-nitrosoureas (I; X=O, Y=NO), 3-(benzothiazolyl-2)-1-(2-chloroethyl)-1-nitrosoureas (II; X=O, Y=NO), 3-(cycloalkyl)-1-(2-chloroethyl)-

hydrochloric acid (0.1 N) in the medium of either dichloromethane or chloroform. The dilute acid conditions were selected so as to favour the formation of unprotonated nitrous acid and N₂O₃. Since these species are harder acids than the nitrosonium ion or its derivatives which is formed at a highly acidic condition, they were expected to favour electrophilic attack at the harder nitrogen of the thioureas rather at the competing soft sulphur atom. In the event, when a suspension of the thioureas and sodium nitrite in dichloromethane or chloroform at -5° was treated dropwise with one equivalent of 0.1 N HCl, a yellow colour is slowly developed and on

1-nitrosoureas (III; X=O, Y=NO, n=4-6) and bis(2-chloroethyl)-1-nitrosourea)alkane (IV; X=O, Y=NO, n=2-4) have been synthesised by the nitrosation of the respective ureas in a suspension or solution of water using sodium nitrite and formic acid. The ureas were obtained by heating a mixture of amines or diamines with β-chloroethylisocyanate either in the medium of water or ethanol. The corresponding nitrosothioureas (I, II, III and IV; X=S, Y=NO) were synthesised from the respective thioureas by nitrosation using sodium nitrite and dilute

normal working resulted in the isolation of the novel N-nitrosothioureas. When nitrosation of the thiourea was carried out at higher concentration of acid (3-5 N) the corresponding ureas were obtained (I, II and III; X=O, Y=H) instead of nitroso derivatives. This type of conversion of thiourea to urea in higher acidic conditions has been reported by several investigators⁵.

Antitumor activity: A few nitrosourea and nitrosothiourea derivatives have been screened for their

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antitumor activity by *in vivo* against the transplanted mouse leukemia L1210 by using the method reported by Bradner *et al.*⁶. The compounds were administered in an olive oil suspension for 8 days consecutively using *N,N*-bis(2-chloroethyl)-*N*-nitroso-urea (BCNU) as standard. The antitumor activity of the compounds was evaluated by measuring the median survival time whose results were expressed as percent T/C (MST treated/MST control) $\times$ 100. The test results have been shown in Table 2. Among

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF NITROSO DERIVATIVES ON L1210 LEUKEMIA*

Dose mg/kg	III (X=O, Y=S, n=4)		III (X=S, Y=O, n=4)	
	TC %	Surv.	TC %	Surv.
1	104	0	94	1
4	240	1	100	1
8	470	8	162	0
16	470	6	200	0
32	156	0	200	0

* Tumor inoculum: 10^4 leukemia cell per mouse implanted; Treatment: single dose; Evaluation: median survival time (MST); Result TC=MST treated/MST control $\times$ 100; Criteria, TC more than 120 significant block; Surv.=Number of mice surviving at 30 days.

the compounds tested, III (X=S, Y=NO, n=4) was found to be the most active inhibitor against leukemia L1210 in producing long term survival. The percent T/C value of this compound was found to be 470 in a dose of 16 mg/kg of the body weight of the mouse.

Experimental

The ir spectra were taken on Perkin-Elmer 293 spectrophotometer.

3-(4-Phenylthiazolyl-2)-1-(2-chloroethyl)urea (I; R=C₆H₅, X=O, Y=H): A mixture of 2-amino-4-phenylthiazole (1.8 g) and 2-chloroethylisocyanate (1.1 ml) in a suspension of water was heated on water bath for 1 h during which a clear solution was obtained. After cooling it was stirred overnight and the precipitate, thus obtained, was filtered, dried and crystallised from ethanol to yield the product (1.2 g, 36%), m.p. 120-122° (Found: S, 11.18. C₁₂H₁₂N₂SOCl requires S, 11.38%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3320 (br., NH), 2920 (CH₂ stretching), 1700 (C=O) and 1600 cm⁻¹ (C-N stretch).

Similarly, I (R=*p*-chlorophenyl, X=O, Y=H), m.p. 116°; II (X=O, Y=H), m.p. 164-167°; III (n=4, X=O, Y=H), m.p. 80°; III (n=5, X=O, Y=H), m.p. 122°; III (n=6, X=O, Y=H), m.p. 119°; IV (n=2, X=O, Y=H), m.p. 144°; IV (n=3, X=O, Y=H), m.p. 192° and IV (n=4, X=O, Y=H), m.p. 204° have been prepared from their respective amines.

3-(4-Phenylthiazolyl-2)-1-(2-chloroethyl)thiourea (I; X=S, Y=H): A mixture of 2-amino-4-phenylthiazole (1.8 g) and 2-chloroethylisocyanate (1.5 ml) in absolute alcohol (20 ml) was refluxed for 1 h.

After cooling, the desired product was separated as colourless crystals (1.8 g, 60%), m.p. 186° (Found: S, 21.25. C₁₂H₁₂N₂S₂Cl requires S, 21.47%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3300 (br., NH), 2900 (CH₂ stretching), 1600 cm⁻¹ (C-N stretch).

Similarly, II (X=S, Y=H), m.p. 206° (Found: S, 21.22. C₁₂H₁₂N₂S₂Cl requires S, 23.53%); III (n=4, X=S, Y=H), m.p. 145° (Found: S, 15.30. C₆H₁₁N₂S₂Cl requires S, 15.46%); III (n=5, X=S, Y=H), m.p. 175° (Found: S, 14.18. C₆H₁₁N₂S₂Cl requires S, 14.74%); III (n=6, X=S, Y=H), m.p. 181° (Found: S, 13.60. C₁₀H₁₀N₂S₂Cl requires S, 13.85%); IV (n=2, X=S, Y=H), m.p. 127° (Found: S, 21.30. C₈H₁₀N₂S₂Cl₂ requires S, 21.12%); and IV (n=3, X=S, Y=H), m.p. 166° (Found: S, 20.25. C₆H₁₀N₂S₂Cl₂ requires S, 20.18%) were prepared.

3-(4-Phenylthiazolyl-2)-1-(2-chloroethyl)-1-nitroso-urea (I; R=C₆H₅, X=O, Y=NO): To a solution of the I (R=C₆H₅, X=O, Y=H) (1.2 g) in 85% formic acid (30 ml) sodium nitrate (1.1 g) was added under ice-cooling with stirring. After 1 h, it was diluted with equal volume of water and kept overnight. The desired compound separated as colourless crystals (0.6 g, 35%), m.p. 247° (Found: S, 10.08. C₁₂H₁₁N₂SO₂Cl requires S, 10.27%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3350 (br., NH), 2900 (CH₂ stretch), 1700 (C=O) and 1540 cm⁻¹ (C-N stretch).

3-(4-Phenylthiazolyl-2)-1-(2-chloroethyl)-1-nitrosothiourea (I; R=C₆H₅, X=S, Y=NO): To a suspension of the thiourea (I; R=C₆H₅, X=S) (0.30 g) and sodium nitrite (0.2 g) in dichloromethane (100 ml), dilute HCl (20 ml, 0.1 N) was added dropwise with stirring at 0° for 0.5 h. After the addition was completed the reaction mixture was warmed with stirring and kept overnight at room temperature. The organic layer was removed, dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and solvent evaporated. The crude nitrosothiourea was purified by crystallisation in cold ethanol (0.2 g, 60%), m.p. 207° (Found: S, 18.32. C₁₂H₁₁N₂S₂OCl requires S, 18.54%).

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF NITROSO DERIVATIVES

Compd. no.	Nitroso ureas, I (X=O, Y=NO)		Nitroso thioureas, I (X=S, Y=NO)	
	M.p.	%Sulphur Found/ (Calcd.)	M.p.	%Sulphur Found/ (Calcd.)
I, R= <i>p</i> -chloro-phenyl	256	8.78 (8.91)	>250	17.19 (17.07)
II	>250	11.05 (11.22)	>250	21.12 (21.26)
III, n=4	72°	18.72** (19.09)	281	18.96 (18.68)
III, n=5	90°	—	225	12.54 (12.80)
III, n=6	110°	—	246	12.26 (12.12)
IV, n=2	144°	25.68** (25.53)	194	17.68 (17.73)
IV, n=3	165°	—	205	17.14 (17.06)

* Recrystallised from petroleum ether.
** Nitrogen %.

The other nitrosoureas and nitrosothioureas have been listed in Table I.

When the nitrosation was carried out by the gradual addition of HCl (3 N) by taking the above thiourea and sodium nitrite in equivalent proportions, a deep red colouration developed which gradually turned bluish, and after heating to room temperature, fine particles of sulphur appeared on the surface. These were separated and usual work up procedure with the organic layer gave a colourless solid which was found to be identical to I ($R = C_6H_5$, $X = O$, $Y = H$).

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